

Performance advancement of a new sub-micron pore size polymeric foam for vacuum insulation panels

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ABSTRACT

This work demonstrates the advancements towards the use of a submicron- pore size polymeric foams (SUMFOAM) as core for Vacuum Insulation Panels (VIPs). The results of the 3rd generation foam show a remarkable total thermal conductivity below 5 mW/m·K in vacuum. Under atmospheric conditions, values similar to the thermal conductivity of still air (26 mW/m·K) are achieved. The suitability of SUMFOAM as core for VIPs was evaluated for a real sized transport box, resulting in similar thermal performance compared to the box made with standard fumed silica cores.

KEYWORDS

vacuum insulation panel, polymeric foam, thermal conductivity, sub-micron pore sizes, open porous materials

INTRODUCTION

In Europe, buildings account for almost 40% of total energy consumption with the majority being spent by the heating sector (space and water heating and appliances - refrigerators and freezers). In cold chain logistics, there is an increasing need for high autonomy (passive cooling solutions), high temperature maintenance time of the goods to be delivered and an optimal volume capacity by shipment. By being up to 10 times better than existing solutions, VIPs save considerably valuable space and resources.

The newly developed sub-micron pore size polymeric foam, by the company SUMTEQ, is the first high-performance and scalable polymeric material to industrial applications. In contrast to aerogels, a time-consuming drying process is not needed. Results of the 1st and 2nd generation foams were shown by Almeida et al. (2017). The former revealed open pores below 1 μm , but the thermal conductivities λ in vacuum were still too high (up to 20 mW/m·K). The 2nd generation foams were prepared with opacifiers, which decreased λ to values of ~ 7 mW/m·K. But these presented larger pore sizes of about 5 μm , which is considered too high for long-term applications in comparison to fumed silica. Advances towards the 3rd generation foam and its suitability as core material for VIPs are presented here.

METHODS

SUMFOAM (SF) was produced by the company SUMTEQ GmbH following the method developed by Strey et al. (2015). Several foams of different co-polymer composition (as PS- and PMMA-based), additives, autoclave parameters (pressure, temperature and time) and foam expansion rate were tested. All the foams were prepared containing carbon based opacifier material. Samples in the sizes of (12x12x1.5) cm³ were manufactured and characterized in terms of thermal conductivity dependence on air pressure. For this, the same procedure and equations

as described by Almeida et. al (2017) are used. For building the prototype transport box, 4 panels of (30x27.5x3) cm³ and 2 panels of (32x32x3) cm³ were produced. Figure 1 shows a representative real size core and VIP panel made of SF and its assembly as a transport box system.

Figure 1. Real size panels made of SUMFOAM before and after evacuation and the assembly of the transport box.

Heat loss value (Q value) test: The test uses a fan heater for introducing thermal energy into the packaging system. The electrical power used to keep the inner temperature of the box along the test time divided by the temperature difference of inside and outside the box, determine the Q value of the component. The box was placed inside a cooling chamber at 0°C while the inside temperature was set to 30 °C ($\Delta T = 30$ K).

Performance test: The qualification of the box is done according to the International Safe Transit Association 7D summer scenario (ISTA 7D, 2007). The target of this test is the evaluation of the duration of temperature stability of the inner temperature between +2.0°C and +8.0°C. To stabilize the temperature inside the box, phase change materials (PCMs) pre-conditioned to ~3°C were placed inside the boxes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thermal conductivity measurements

Gas pressure influence on the thermal conductivity of several types of SUMFOAM (SF) and conventional cores for VIPs is presented in Figure 2. Fumed silica (FS) still has the smallest gas pressure dependence on thermal conductivity of all the core materials. It has a total thermal conductivity in vacuum of 4 mW/m·K, which doubles at gas pressures as high as 100 mbar. The major difference compared to the other commercial cores is the pore size. While FS has pores in the nanometric scale (~ 0.4 μm), thus in the same order of magnitude of the mean free path of air molecules, PU foam and glass fibre have considerable larger pore diameters (~ 130 μm and 60 μm , respectively). Besides that, glass fibres presented the so-called “coupling effect”, related to the gas in between the intermediate spaces of the fibres creating additional pathways to heat conduction (Fricke et al., 2006).

The curves of the 1st, SF-(1G) and the 2nd, SF-(2G) generations of polymeric foams presented by Almeida et al. (2017) are plotted on Figure 2 for comparison. As reported, the high radiation and solid thermal contributions of SF of the 1st generation yield a total thermal conductivity in vacuum of more than 20 mW/m·K. The macro-defects in between the foam granules cause the rise of the thermal conductivity at gas pressures below 10 mbar, but the very small pore sizes of this foam (~ 0.4 μm) are able to suppress the gas conductivity in a similar way as FS. This can be visible by the shape of the data fitting, where the second inflection point of the “S-shape” curve happens at gas pressures above 1000 mbar for both materials. On the other hand, the thermal conductivity of the 2nd generation SF in vacuum presents much lower values, close to

the start value of PU. However, these foams do not have pores at the sub-micrometer level and gas conductivity starts to rise at gas pressures below 10 mbar.

Figure 2. Thermal conductivity as function of internal gas (air) pressure for the SUMFOAM cores of the 1st (1G), 2nd (2G) and 3rd (3G) generation in comparison to conventional core materials.

Advancements by keeping the fine structure of SUMFOAM while keeping a low total thermal conductivity can be seen in Figure 2. All the SF materials of the 3rd generation have a thermal conductivity in vacuum very similar to fumed silica (~ 4 to 5 mW/m·K). As a result of their small pores (mostly below 1 μm), the thermal conductivities of the majority of the SF foams at atmospheric conditions are similar to or even below that of still air (~ 26 mW/m·K). However, the foams also have micrometric gaps in between the foam particles, mostly in between 12 μm and 50 μm size and 10% to 20% in volume. Despite this and in order to keep the thermal conductivity below 10 mW/m·K, the internal gas pressure can be extended up to 50 mbar.

Thermal performance of SUMFOAM transport box prototype

Heat loss value (Q-value) test: It describes the energy loss of a component per time and temperature difference. The smaller the Q value, the better are the insulation properties. The test was carried out for about 67 hours to analyze a longer-term thermal behavior of the tested box. The average temperatures in and out of the box were 32.7 °C and 0.1 °C, respectively. With an injected electric power given by the heater of 4.02 W, the calculated Q-value of the SF-box is 0.12 W/K. The Q-value of the standard transport boxes made with fumed silica panels is 0.11 ± 0.01 W/K, similar to SF-box.

Performance test: Figure 3 presents the test protocol of temperature over time of the transport boxes built with SF-VIPs (bluish curves) and fumed silica VIPs (black curves), respectively. Inside and outside temperatures are plotted. It shows the dynamic response of the temperatures inside the boxes when subjected to the external multi-level summer temperature profiles in the range of 22 °C to 35 °C (night and days summer simulation) along the time. It can be seen that the inner temperatures of both boxes are very similar and have comparable response to the external profile.

Figure 3 also shows that the performance time, i.e. the time span until the average value of the temperature sensors inside the box exceeds the +8.0°C, is very similar for both boxes: 40 hours for the SF-box and 42 hours for the fumed silica one. With a deviation of only 5%, it can be considered that this first SUMFOAM box prototype performs similar to the conventional ones under the tested conditions. However, more tests are needed to get statistically valid data for a new transport box built with SUMFOAM-VIPs.

Figure 3. Performance test of transport boxes built with fumed silica VIPs (black curves) and SUMFOAM-VIPs (bluish curves) under ISTA 7D (2007) summer profile.

CONCLUSIONS

The thermal conductivity measurements of the 3rd generation SUMFOAM have shown that low thermal conductivities in the range of 4 to 5 mW/m·K can be achieved, which is similar to fumed silica boards. Real size prototype SUMFOAM-VIPs were produced and integrated into a standard transport box from the va-Q-tec portfolio. All the necessary steps for the production of such a commercial box turned out to be applicable with SUMFOAM panels as well, meaning that there are no changes in the production process.

The prototype box was tested under established internal procedures and compared to boxes with fumed silica panels. Heat loss (Q-Value test) and performance (ISTA 7D summer scenario) tests of SUMFOAM-VIP prototype box revealed similar values to the conventional fumed silica ones. This is due to the comparable thermal conductivity in vacuum of both types of cores, as well as to the identical assembly of the box system.

Further research is being conducted for the suitability of SUMFOAM-VIPs for building applications. Also, aging factors in addition to the gas pressure increase are under investigation.

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